

REVIEW NOTE

HOW TO IMPROVE OUR WORLD

Cómo mejorar nuestro mundo

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ABSTRACT. *A better world is possible by solving the major problems that threaten the existence of humanity: intensive pollution, climate change accelerated by global warming, exponential population growth, and a tremendously unfair speculative economic system.*

KEYWORDS. *Improve our world; pollution; global warming; climate change; exponential population growth; economic system; spirituality.*

RESUMEN. *Un mundo mejor es posible si se resuelven los grandes problemas que amenazan la existencia de la humanidad: la contaminación intensiva, el cambio climático acelerado por el calentamiento global, el crecimiento exponencial de la población y un sistema económico especulativo tremendamente injusto.*

PALABRAS CLAVE. *Mejorar nuestro mundo; contaminación; calentamiento global; cambio climático; crecimiento exponencial de la población; sistema económico; espiritualidad.*

Introduction

A better world is possible. Men of science must be intelligent and should contribute to solving the ills that plague our world.

Evil lies behind all of them and the only way to fight it is with goodness. Today it is more important than ever to have an open mind and to free it from egoistic prejudices.

This brief contribution draws attention to the pressing problems that burden both the present and the future of humanity, proposing solutions that can be

implemented as long as the malicious powers that pull the strings do not prevent it.

Humanity must choose which path to follow: wickedness that leads to disaster or goodness that offers an opportunity to avoid it. This is not an ethical philosophy but an open reflection that should be considered by all people of good-will.

Major Problems Threatening Our World

Global warming (Zandalinas *et al.* 2021) caused mainly by mankind is accelerating all of us towards unfavorable climate change. Exponential population growth (Malthus 1798; Meadows *et al.* 2018) is also posing a serious threat. Both problems must be controlled and solved as soon as possible.

Time is pressing. Our future is in danger, and this planet cannot wait any longer. This planet is sick of our permanent aggressions. Nature must be respected, and the damage caused must be reversed. The current economic system of highly speculative capitalism (Marx 1873; Robinson 2014) must be transformed to make it possible.

Global warming is accelerating climate change. We know that it is a complex problem involving various factors such as solar activity and volcanic eruptions among others, but mankind seems to be the main cause of this dangerous process that is becoming irreversible.

Nature has been exploited by mankind without any respect, generating enormous land and sea pollution that has contributed decisively to global warming. Humans have appropriated their natural environment to destroy or alter it. What right do we have as an animal species to do so? And the most advanced civiliza-

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tions have subjugated, enslaved, or exterminated other less-developed societies. In the same way, we have ended the existence of countless innocent living beings using our supposed superiority as justification. This model of civilization is unviable. We are reaching a dead end. We cannot go on like this.

Exponential population growth is a demographic bomb that will soon explode. There will be no resources to sustain it and the current economic system will not be able to assimilate such a large population. If this is not done, poverty, misery, violence, and conflicts will inevitably grow to unsuspected limits. In order to solve this serious problem, birth control must be introduced, especially in the most densely populated countries.

Human beings can choose between good and evil. The vast majority prefer the second option because it is the easier one. This world is not what it seems. It really hides the real hell with a deceptive appearance, even paradisiacal in some places.

Those who choose the first option, that is, good, will encounter all sorts of obstacles in their lives. That is the hardest and most painful path that only a few follow to the end. However, those who succeed obtain the only true prize that our existence in this world grants: the liberation of our soul and infinite knowledge forever.

It may seem like a small thing, but it is the greatest treasure that this life offers us, even if it costs so much to obtain it.

Choosing evil gives you power and wealth, but you completely misunderstand the meaning of your life. You lose the opportunity to save your soul, which will never be free in the afterlife.

The tremendous advance of technology is not only conditioning our freedom of thought but is making it

easier than ever for evil to manipulate and control us. We must take this into account in order not to fall into this trap.

Conclusion: Improving Our World

A peaceful revolution must be launched against the evil that dominates this world. This evil is the cause of all the serious human problems that plague our world.

The current society generated by the dominant economic system is profoundly unequal and unjust. It is impossible to move toward a just society unless we change the highly speculative capitalist economic system that controls our lives.

We must move towards an egalitarian society based on kindness that makes possible a much more just world where everyone can live in dignity. This is the only way to solve the serious problems that damage our planet and threaten the continuity of humanity.

Every good and wise person has a spiritual dimension. This makes it possible to fight against evil and improve our world. We may have lost many battles but not the war. There is still hope.

Please do not confuse spirituality with religion (Friedman & Friedman 2008). Traditionally, religion has been at the service of established power by manipulating spirituality to control people.

We live in critical times. It is time to act, to take action, and fight against the evil that plagues our world. If we do not do it now, we will not be able to save it.

To be continued. This is not the end. We will continue trying to improve this world by fighting against evil. This is the beginning of the end for those who have enslaved humanity and are destroying our planet.

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